

Rambutan (*Nephelium lappaceum* L.): The nutritional and functional properties

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Abstract

Rambutan (Nephelium lappaceum L.) is a tropical fruit that grows naturally in Southeast Asia, most especially in the Philippines, particularly in Visayas and northern Luzon regions. This fruit has a special outer skin and a sweet, delicious core, which people like not just the taste, but also because of its health and medicinal benefits. Rambutan contains essential nutrients such as glucose, potassium, calcium, fiber, and B vitamins, which help keep the body healthy. The peel also has useful substances such as tannins, carbohydrates, flavonoids, and phenolic compounds, thereby helping protect the body from damage and reduce inflammation. The seeds possess some good properties, such as antibacterial, antifungal, and other pharmaceutical benefits. In addition, rambutan could help with diabetes, cancer, and other diseases. Some chemicals found in rambutan such as ellagic acid, corilagin, and geraniin, have shown potential in medicine. However, there are some problems to overcome, including the outer coating of the seeds which may be harmful, and getting certain active ingredients from the fruit is difficult and expensive. Despite these, rambutan remains a potential source of both food and medicine. Further studies are needed to make full use of all its benefits.

Keywords: Rambutan; Fruit; Nutritional properties; Functional properties.

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Introduction

The Philippines is home to various species of wildlife, plants, and organisms that are all unique to this archipelago. The Philippines has two seasons per year it being dry and the wet season; due to this climate, it boasts a number of plants and fruits who have acclimated to this climate. One such adaptation to this is by developing or growing exterior layers and shells to survive in this tropical country. One such plant that has done this is the rambutan (*Nephelium lappaceum* L.) in the family of *Sapindaceae*, are fruits that are commonly found in humid tropical regions of southeast Asia. Synonyms include *Dimocarpus crinitus* Lour., *Euphoria crinita* Poir., *Euphoria nephelium* Poir., *Euphoria nephelium* DC., *Euphoriramb-outan* Labill., *Scytalia crinita* Raeusch., and *Scytalia ramboutan* Roxb.

In the Philippines, it is seen as a common fruit that is eaten by locals in the Visayas and northern Luzon regions, due to it being more frequent in those areas. It is an iconic fruit that entices locals to remember eating it due to its unique structure and sweet flavored texture; to properly eat it, one must break to open its outer layer to reach the core of the fruit, which is usually the one that is eaten. Commercially, it can be seen packaged in cans, being sold into markets, or being able to eat it fresh on the street with the vendors selling it in local cities.

Ever since its history the rambutan has always been used as a form of dessert or appetizer by people and is mostly seen as food to be eaten. However, throughout the years, researchers have been interested in the unique structure of the rambutan and if it holds anything of value within its structure in the field of science that may create new discoveries. The target has been from various parts of the rambutan from the seeds and its outer shell layer. According to Solidum (2012), the outer layer of rambutan peels contain the phytochemical tannins in the shell and contains carbohydrates, when isolated using stock solutions of carbohydrate extraction. With this knowledge in hand, the peels of rambutan contain properties that may be valuable in the future.

Additionally, Chai et al. (2018) suggests that the seeds from the rambutan have phytochemical properties that can be extracted from it, namely tannins and saponins, and the quality of the extraction of these said phytochemicals can be enhanced by the process of turning. It is also told that the fat from fermented rambutan seeds can be used as cacao butter for culinary purposes. This means that both the outer layer and inner layer of rambutan has properties in which both parts of the rambutan contain something of value for the pharmaceutical industry. Additionally, rambutan contains various other benefits contained within it. According to Shahrajabian et al. (2020), rambutan contains various other macromolecules such as glucose, potassium, magnesium, calcium, fiber, and several other B vitamins, proving that rambutan by itself that it has various benefits that can be obtained from it without going to the strain of strenuous experimentations and extracting the pure extract that is contained within it.

Reportedly, Mistriyani et al. (2021) have discovered and experimented regarding the anti-oxidative capabilities of rambutan peels. The peels of rambutans that are usually thrown after eating, contains strong anti-oxidants after extraction by maceration and using methanol as the solvent for extraction (Mistriyani et al., 2021). It contains high amounts of phenols and flavonoids. Additionally, Azzatul et al. (2020) said that the seed of rambutan also contains anti-bacterial and anti-fungal properties, albeit not as potent as the peels. They also contain major fatty acids that is contained within the seed, namely palmitic, stearic, oleic, and arachidic oils. They have also introduced that powders of fried rambutan seeds are known to be used as local medicine or supplementary medicine for locals in Malaysia.

Methodology

The study was designed to collect and analyze scientific information about *Nephelium lappaceum* L., which is commonly called rambutan. The process involved searching and reviewing primary scientific sources from trusted databases and journals. This was to gather accurate and current information on the nutritional content, chemical compounds, medicinal effects, and possible uses of rambutan in medicine and nutrition.

Sources of Data and Literature Search

The main sources of information were online scientific databases and digital libraries. These were selected for a wide range of peer-reviewed articles and reliable scientific content. The databases used included:

- SciFinder
- Scopus
- Google Scholar
- PubMed
- Web of Science
- ScienceDirect

In addition to these academic resources, the scientific and common names of rambutan were checked and confirmed using the World Flora Online (WFO) Plant List (<https://wfoplantlist.org/>), which is a trusted source for plant classification. This ensured that the identification and grouping of *Nephelium lappaceum* L. were accurate across all the studies reviewed.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

To ensure that the sources reviewed were relevant and of good quality, specific criteria were applied when selecting the studies:

Inclusion Criteria:

- Articles with high-quality experimental or review data on the medical, chemical, or nutritional aspects of rambutan.
- Studies that focus on specific parts of rambutan such as its active compounds (e.g., flavonoids, tannins, saponins), its health effects (e.g., anti-inflammatory or anti-cancer properties), and its use in the pharmaceutical industry.
- Research published in respected peer-reviewed journals.
- Studies that have English abstracts.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Non-peer-reviewed studies, documents that are not officially published (grey literature), and articles that do not use clear scientific methods.
- Studies that focus on rambutan in food preparation but not associating with health or nutrition.
- Articles that are outdated or lack enough method details to be properly checked.

Data Collection Process

The data collection process focused on articles published from 2010 onwards to include the latest research. Keywords such as “*Nephelium lappaceum*,” “*rambutan*,” “*phytochemicals*,” “*nutritional value*,” “*pharmacological activities*,” and “*medicinal properties*” were used to find relevant studies. Boolean operators like AND and OR were used to narrow down the search and find the most suitable studies for the review. The chosen studies were thoroughly examined. Key details such as ethnomedicinal uses, chemical composition, and pharmacological effects were gathered and organized in a clear manner. The synthesis process also included comparing results from different studies to find out their similarities and differences and to show which findings were the most reliable and which areas still needed more research.

The Nutritional Value of Rambutan Fruit

Table 1. Nutritional Value of Rambutan Fruit

Composition	Quantity
Fat	0.68%
Protein	0.91%
Nitrogen	0.14%
Ash	0.33%
Calcium	9.58 mg/100g
Iron	0.34 mg/100g
Magnesium	12.3 mg/100g
Manganese	1.06 mg/100g
Potassium	84.1 mg/100g
Sodium	20.8mg/100g
Zinc	0.17 mg/100g
Phosphorus	16.6 mg/100g
pH	4.66
Vitamin A	< 40 IU/100g
Vitamin C	59.4mg/100g
Fructose	2.9%
Glucose	2.9%
Sucrose	11.4%
Maltose	<0.1%
Lactose	<0.1%
Total Sugars	17.2%
Riboflavin	0.050 mg/100g
Thiamin	<0.010 mg/100g
Fiber	0.05%

Rambutan, which is often not overlooked, actually has some good nutritional benefits (Issara et al., 2014). They have a moderate amount of important nutrients such as macronutrients, micronutrients, and sugars, which could be helpful in some diets. Rambutan has small amounts of fat (0.68%) and protein (0.91%), but not enough to be a major source of these nutrients. Still, they can be part of a balanced diet. It stands out because of the good amounts of potassium and vitamin C. Moreover, they also have some calcium, magnesium, and phosphorus, which are important for keeping bones strong and helping the body's chemical processes work properly.

The fruit has a fairly high sugar content, with about 17.2% mostly formed by sucrose, glucose, and fructose. However, the exact digestibility and impact on blood sugar would depend on how much they can eat. The fruit is slightly acidic with a pH of 4.66, which may affect the taste and digestion. It also has very little fiber (0.05%), which does not help in adding fiber to their diet. Even though rambutan is not high in protein or fat, it offers a mix of vitamins and minerals such as potassium and vitamin C, along with a moderate sugar level. It could be a nice addition to a diet that focuses on getting more micronutrients.

Chemical Constituents

Various chemicals compounds were found inside the rambutan. The following phytochemicals are Carbohydrates, Alkaloids, Steroids, Sterols, Glycosides, Flavonoids, Triterpenoids, Tannins, Proteins, and Amino Acids. Additionally, studies done by Thitilertdecha et al. (2010) isolation and identification of active compounds/constituents were processed using lipid peroxidation inhibition assays.

The isolated compounds were identified as ellagic acid (EA) (1), corilagin (2) and geraniin (3) (Lim, 2013). These compounds accounted for 69.3% of methanolic extract, with geraniin (56.8%) as the major component, which suggests that these compounds that were present inside the peels may be used for pharmaceutical purposes with enough evidence.

Pharmacological Activities

With the widespread recognition that the rambutan fruit gets due to its rarity and unique structure, researchers have tested and experimented various ways in which the rambutan or parts of it could have any health benefits that may lead to long term improvement of an individual. From the data gathered from various studies, the rambutan has shown that it's efficacy on anti-inflammatory properties, anti-diabetic properties, anti-bacterial property, and lastly anti-cancer properties. Within the gathered data these functions are the ones who have gained much research about the inherent properties of rambutan. However, one such negative aspect of this, is that the seed coating of rambutan contains narcotic and analgesic properties if not careful may lead to serious repercussions upon the user, so this is a factor that is to beware of.

Anti-tumor properties

A study done by Fang and Ng (2015) shows that by the compound NLTl (*N. lappaceum* trypsin inhibitor), it was identified through the isolation of said compound in liquid chromatography. After all these processes they have discovered that the compound NLTl has a dose dependent inhibitory effect on tumor cells. It is considered as one of the few nitric oxide inducing activity that aids in inhibitory suppression.

Anti-oxidative properties

The rambutan peels are reported to have anti-oxidant properties by using anti-radical, ferric reducing activity, chelating agents, beta chelating agents, and lipid peroxidation methods reportedly by Embuscado (2015, as cited by Rahman, 2017).

Anti-bacterial properties

According to Phuong et al. (2020) evaluation by use of methanolic extracts, in vitro, and situ methods, yielded results of microbial activity against some species of Gram negative and Gram-positive bacteria from their current studies.

Conclusions

Overall, the rambutan is a fruit that holds many possibilities of being local delicacy and a pharmaceutical tool to create new drugs. From its sweet and tasty flavors to the various beneficial and nutritional compounds that it holds within, there are other various factors that have to be supplemented by future researchers such as the narcotic and analgesic properties that its seed coating has when eaten negligibly. It has acute or sub-chronic toxicity, and the methods of extracting the specific compounds that a researcher wants to be very time consuming and costly. Regardless, the possibilities of this fruit have yet to reach its full capacity and it will be beneficial for future researchers to gauge the full capacity of *Nephelium lappaceum* L.

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